

Lesson Learned from Infections of Covid-19 Prevention: From Primary School Students' Parents in Surat Thani

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has been severe in the past situation. It affects everyone's physical and mental health. Economic, social, living conditions, and the education system that need to be adjusted to the way students learn. Changing the teaching methods of teachers and parents in order to supervise their children to overcome such a turning situation, and as a result of the situation, the research team was interested in taking the lessons learned on parental care in cognitive issues. Attitude, prevention, and adaptation in the above situations. The majority of respondents were female parents aged 41 years and over, with bachelor's degrees, employed or private sector employees, and parents with two children aged 6-7 years. Have the highest level of protective behavior for your child. They are well adapted physically, mentally, academically, socially, and environmentally, and are well prepared to prevent coronavirus infection.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, Lesson learned, Parents, Primary school students

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INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, which has been raging around the world since late 2019, has affected all sectors, both economically and socially, as well as affecting people's physical and emotional health who fear infection¹ It causes stress from adaptation and affects living conditions. finance Career² It also affects the education systems all over the world that are unable to open their classes normally. Therefore, the teaching and learning style needs to be adjusted to keep up with the events. Shift from classroom learning to home learning Blended and online learning. However, Thailand has adjusted its education system in this situation. The Ministry of Education, which oversees the management of basic education, has established a policy on teaching and learning in crisis situations through online distance learning. Eclectic style Under the concept of learning-led education. School may stop but learning can't³. More importantly, in addition to responsible agencies must adapt. Families or parents of students also have to adapt to their children's teaching, but with leaps and bounds that are not prepared in advance, parents face many problems. Although schools prepare for the most effective learning arrangements, there are still problems and obstacles that arise for parents, which require parents to spend time supporting their children's learning and incur

additional costs. In addition, it must manage the issue of preventing the spread of germs that occur and affect the physical and mental health of students. Teaching and learning, especially teaching where parents have to change their roles from parents to teachers. Build the house into a classroom for both physical and social environments. Based on this data, the panel was interested in removing parents' lessons on how to deal with the problem. This is a transcription or summary of past experiences in various aspects⁴ through awareness of knowledge, understanding, attitudes, adaptation to situations, and prevention of COVID-19 infection for primary school students in Surat Thani province. The results of this lesson will be useful for applying to overcome crises and preparing for future pandemics.

METHODS

Study design

This research is quantitative, surveying cognitive opinions. Parents' attitudes about COVID-19 affecting the care of their children Prevention and adaptation behavior to prevent COVID-19 infection among parents of primary school students in Surat Thani province, a province in southern Thailand.

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Study sample and sample size

In this research, the population is parents of elementary school students. 90,568 persons (Office of Social Development and Human Security, 2022) The team used the Taro Yamane formula to obtain the right sample size. With calculations from the formula $n = N/(1 + Ne^2)^5$ which n is the sample size, n is the population, and e is the tolerance, which in the research is 0.05 from the formula, $n=90,568/(1+90568*(0.052))$, so $n=398.24$. However, to prevent errors in data collection and questionnaire responses of samples that may occur. The sample size of 450 people was obtained by selecting sampling without using the principle of nonprobability sampling but using the convenience sampling method.

Data collection

We collected data between January and March 2023, with primary data collected from questionnaires via Google Forms. Cognition and attitude about COVID-19 infection among parents of primary school students in Surat Thani province that affect the care of their children Prevention and adaptation behavior for COVID-19 prevention for primary school students of parents in Surat Thani province The secondary data section is collected from documents, articles, etc. Books & Online Media.

Statistical analysis

After collecting information from respondents, The research team examined the data and formulated the code before preparing the data table. Data was collected and analyzed using SPSS 23.0 software and descriptive statistics that showed frequencies. Percentage, average, and standard deviation⁶

RESULTS

In this research, the majority of respondents were female parents. 84.7% (381) were 41 years of age or older. 28.7% (129) had a bachelor's degree. 40.4% (182) Marital status 6.4% (254) Average monthly income 5,000-10,000 baht 31.1% (140) Employment 30.7% (138) Relationship with students as parents 86.7% (390) Number of children in care 41.3% (186) Children aged 6-7 years 41.8% (188) The results are shown by objective. as follows, Objective 1 Study knowledge and understanding about COVID-19 Parents of primary school students in Surat Thani It was found that parents knew that COVID-19 was the first outbreak in the country. People's Republic of China 91.1% (410) The spread of COVID-19 spreads through the air. 64.4% (290) This pathogen has an incubation period of 7 days. 58.9% (265) Non-COVID-19 symptoms are: excessive sweating 84.7% (381) The way to prevent COVID-19 is not to enter crowded places. 91.3% (411) Objective 2: To study the attitudes of parents of primary school students in Surat Thani province regarding the COVID-19 pandemic affecting their children's care, it was found that the majority of parents have the opinion that COVID-19 can be transmitted in the air to their

children at the highest level. 47.3% (213) It is a disease that is far from their children to a large extent. 26.9% (121) Coronavirus disease 2019 *Andrographis paniculate* can be used to treat or prevent infection in children to a large extent. 40.89 (184) It is a disease that is not dangerous to children and can be cured on its own at a moderate level. 35.78% (161) A good treatment is to wash your hands frequently and wear a mask to reduce the chance of contracting COVID-19 at most. 47.78% (215) Treatment with an aerosol spray or chemicals can kill children to a large extent of COVID-19. 40.44% (182) Individuals in the same household do not need to practice physical distancing to prevent infection with COVID-19 moderately. 34.00% (153) Encouraging children to put food directly in their mouths reduces the chance of contracting COVID-19 at most. 42.00% (189) People within the country are at much lower risk of contracting COVID-19 than people from overseas. 42.00% (189) Individuals returning from abroad and high-risk areas must self-isolate to reduce the risk of contracting COVID-19 at the highest level. 45.56% (205) Objective 3: Parents' behavior in preventing COVID-19 infection for primary school students in Surat Thani province It was found that most parents have behaviors to prevent COVID-19 infection in the following issues: Tell your child to wash their hands with soap or alcohol for at least 20 seconds. Practice regularly 45.33% (204) Have your child wear a surgical or cloth mask while outside the housing facility on a regular basis. 70.22% (316) Tell your child to try to avoid entering crowded areas. 58.89% (265) Tell your child to keep a distance of at least 1-2 meters from others while outside the housing facility. Routine 44.89% (202) Try to get your child to avoid eye contact. Nose and mouth 51.33% (231) Tell your child how to cover their mouth and nose every time they cough or sneeze by using a tissue or the crook of their arms. Practice regularly 55.56% (250) and try to get your child to eat hot or freshly cooked food. Practice regularly 67.56% (304) Encourage children to avoid sharing items with friends or others. 63.11% (284) recommend self-observation to your child when they have a fever, cough, runny nose, and sore throat. The nose does not smell, shortness of breath, tongue, taste perception practice regularly 58.44% (263) Objective 4: Adjustment of parents of primary school students in Surat province to prevent COVID-19. It was found that most parents have adapted to prevent COVID-19 as follows: 1) Physical aspects Parents observed and supervised their children's health at the highest level, 51.56% (232) had their children vaccinated against COVID-19 at the highest level, 43.78% (197), and had observed their children's expressive behavior to a large extent 44.89% (202). 2) Psychological aspects Parents have advised their children to be mentally prepared for any situation to a large extent. 43.33% (195) Parents talk to their children to relieve tension from the situation to a large extent. 43.11% (194) Parents observed their child's expressive behavior at the highest level. 45.56% (205) 3) Academic aspects Parents have adjusted their child's learning and activity plan to a large extent.

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48.22% (217) Parents let their children learn to use the Internet or online networks to a large extent. 44.44% (200) Parents and children adapt to technology by seeking advice on the use of communication devices from knowledgeable or experts at a large level. 44.89% (202) and 4) social and environmental aspects. 36.67% (165) of parents and their children have adapted their home environment to prepare for living at home to a large extent. 47.56% (214) and parents explained their preparedness to prevent the new wave of COVID-19 to a large extent. 44.44% (200)

DISCUSSION

Most of the respondents were female parents aged 41 years or older, with a bachelor's degree, employed as a contractor or private employees. Parental relationships with two children aged 6-7 years, similar to the⁷ Evaluate the Perceived Stress and Coping Strategies among GNM Student of Selected College of Nursing Bhubaneswar during Covid -19 Pandemic Lockdown with parents with bachelor's degrees, living in small families, occupations as private employees. It was found that parents had a good basic knowledge of COVID-19 from countries where the first outbreak occurred. Such outbreaks are spread through the air. They also have knowledge about the symptoms that arise from this infection. In terms of attitude, it was found that parents still have beliefs about the severity of the epidemic, leading to reminders for their children to wash their hands frequently and wear masks as this will reduce the chance of infection and also to remind their children to refrain from putting food directly into their mouths, as well as to practice social distancing with people in the same family to prevent the spread of the disease in the family. It is also the opinion that individuals returning from abroad and high-risk areas must self-quarantine to reduce the risk of contracting COVID-19, which is similar to the COVID-19 prevention behavior of parents of primary school students in Surat Thani province who studied and found that parents have told their children to wash their hands with soap or alcohol for at least 20 seconds, wear masks, maintain a safe social distance (6 feet), wear masks, and practice safe social distancing (6 feet). Get vaccinated against COVID-19 as soon as possible, improve the immune system, and change traditional lifestyles that make it easy to get infected. Just as⁸ tries to get your children to avoid exposure. Explain how to cover your child's mouth and nose every time they cough or sneeze with a tissue or the crook of their arms, and try to get them to eat hot or freshly cooked food. Encourage your child to avoid sharing items with friends or others. Explain self-observation to your child when they have fever symptoms such as cough, runny nose, and/or sore throat. The survey also included comments on COVID-19 from information about parents' disease prevention behavior towards their children, which is in line with the results of lessons learned by parents of primary school students in Surat Thani province about the prevention of COVID-19 infection in this turning situation that found that parents have knowledge and understanding.

Have a positive attitude towards caring for children during the COVID-19 pandemic Have preventive and adaptative behaviors to prepare for COVID-19 by building physical and mental immunity. Parents prioritize observing and taking care of their children's health and have taken their children vaccinated against COVID-19. Talking to your children, being together with family members, and providing an appropriate environment that is conducive to students' learning can be a great way to relieve stress from the COVID-19 pandemic⁹. In addition, parents have observed the expressive behavior of their children. As for education, parents have adjusted their child's care plans and activities. More time for your kids Find a way for your child to learn about using the Internet or online networks, where both parents and children can develop themselves to be able to use technology by seeking advice on how to use communication devices from knowledgeable or experts. It creates a crisis as an opportunity and social and environmental aspects. It has been found that parents have refrained from allowing their children to go out for activities or play outside and have helped to adjust the home environment to quarantine in preparation for living at home, as¹⁰ have attributed to the COVID-19 pandemic as having a significant impact on students' education. Most of them have shifted from school to online instruction. In rural areas, there will be problems with knowledge and understanding of online networking. For this reason, it is necessary to have a teacher or knowledgeable person to help guide them before giving them to their children. As for the social and environmental aspects, it was found that parents have refrained from allowing their children to go out for activities or play outside. Parents and children help adjust the home environment to quarantine and prepare to live at home. Parents also explained how to prepare for the new wave of COVID-19.

CONCLUSIONS

Most respondents are female parents aged 41 years and over. Bachelor's degree Employed or private sector employee Parents with 2 children aged between 6-7 years old Basic knowledge of COVID-19 Able to have a good attitude or opinion about the severity of the epidemic and behaviors to prevent and adapt COVID-19 for primary school students in Surat Thani province. By telling your child to wash their hands with soap or alcohol for at least 20 seconds. Eyes, nose, and mouth. Explaining how to cover your mouth and nose every time you cough or sneeze with a tissue or the crook of your arm, and try to get your child to eat hot or freshly cooked food and observe yourself when you have a fever, cough, runny nose, and/or sore throat. The nose doesn't smell, shortness of breath, and the tongue doesn't sense taste. These data are the knowledge and attitudes of parents of primary school students in Surat Thani province obtained from the lessons learned on the prevention of COVID-19 in a turning situation: a case study of parents of primary school students in Surat Thani province. This will lead to the display of

adaptive behaviors and prevention of infection from the COVID-19 pandemic to children physically, mentally, academically, socially and environmentally to prepare for the prevention of coronavirus infection or any twisted situation that may occur in the future.

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